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CONTRASTIVE PHRASEOLOGY

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Annotation: The main attention is paid to the criteria for selecting idioms, methods of data collection and analysis, as well as comparison of the HSG dictionary with other idiomatic dictionaries. The results of the analysis made it possible to identify unique features of the HSG methodology and offer recommendations for improving approaches to the compilation of idiomatic dictionaries. Finally, limitations of the current study and prospects for future research in this area are discussed.

Keywords: cultural differences, bilingual dictionaries, idiomatic dictionary, methodology, HSG, criteria for choosing idioms, corpus analysis.

Аннотация: Основное внимание уделено критериям выбора идиом, методам сбора и анализа данных, а также сравнению словаря HSG с другими идиоматическими словарями. Результаты анализа позволили выявить уникальные особенности методологии HSG и предложить рекомендации по совершенствованию подходов к составлению идиоматических словарей. Наконец, обсуждаются ограничения текущего исследования и перспективы будущих исследований в этой области.

Ключевые слова: культурные различия, двуязычные словари, идиоматическая лексика, методология, HSG, критерии выбора идиом, корпусный анализ.

Annotatsiya: Asosiy e'tibor idiomalarni tanlash mezonlariga, ma'lumotlarni yig'ish va tahlil qilish usullariga, shuningdek, HSG lug'atini boshqa idiomatik lug'atlar bilan taqqoslashga qaratilgan. Tahlil natijalari HSG metodologiyasining

o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini aniqlash va idiomatik lug'atlarni tuzishga yondashuvlarni takomillashtirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar berish imkonini berdi. Nihoyat, hozirgi tadqiqotning cheklovlari va ushbu sohadagi kelajakdagi tadqiqotlar istiqbollari muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniy farqlar, ikki tilli lug'atlar idiomatik lug'at, metodologiya, HSG, idiom tanlash mezonlari, korpus tahlili.

Contrastive phraseology deals with the comparison of two or more languages. Studies covering three or more languages are rare. Over the past ten years, the languages most often contrasted with German include Russian, Polish, French, Hungarian and Finnish (Palm 1995, 113-114). Swedish, in turn, is also often compared to German (Skoldberg 2004, 9).

J. Smith (1982, 30) emphasizes that the main goal of contrastive phraseology is the comparative analysis of the phraseological systems of two or more languages in order to identify similarities and differences. These results can be applied in practice in translation, teaching and lexicography. Foldes (1996) notes that comparative language analysis can be carried out in different dimensions: interlingual and intralingual. Interlingual comparison focuses on commonalities, similarities, and differences between languages. Intralingual comparison affects multivariance within one language, for example, German. This may include comparison of the phraseology of dialects, regional variants and the standard language. An example would be comparing the phraseological features of different varieties of German, such as "turn every pfennig/every shilling twice", or comparing the phraseology of the German diaspora, such as Hungarian-German, with the phraseology of standard German (Foldes 1996, 17-19; Korhonen Wotjak 2001, 227).

This paper focuses on the cross-linguistic dimension by comparing Swedish and German.

Since the late 1960s, comparative research has been actively carried out in the field of phraseology (Wells 1987, 43). In the 1960s and 1970s, German was most often contrasted with Russian, Polish, Czech, Ukrainian, French and English. In the early 1980s, contrastive phraseology experienced a surge in interest that continues today. In their 2001 paper, Korhonen and Wotjak listed other languages that have been compared to German since the 1980s. Among them are the Germanic languages: Dutch, Swedish, Danish and Icelandic; Romance languages: Spanish and Portuguese; Slovenian languages: Croatian, Slovak and Bulgarian; and Finnish from the Finno-Ugric group (Korhonen and Wotjak, 2001, pp. 228-230).

Despite many studies, there are few contradictory works comparing Swedish and German. In the 1990s, this issue was addressed by researchers such as Kron (1994) and Lund (1992, 1993), who analyzed German and Swedish somatisms. Skog-

Sodersved (1992) examined the frequency of idioms in editorial articles of German and Swedish daily newspapers.

The next section will look at the key terms of phraseology: phraseology, phraseological units and idioms. The emphasis will be on the main characteristics of phraseological units: polylexicality, persistence, idiomaticity and motivation. When considering resilience, three aspects will be considered: psycholinguistic, structural and pragmatic characteristics.

As defined by Palm (1995, 1), phraseology is considered as the science or research discipline concerned with the study of word combinations within a language system. These phrases in a sentence can act as an object of study.

The term “phraseology” has a dual meaning:

1. Linguistic subdiscipline that studies phraseological units (the study of phraseological units).

2. The totality of all phraseological units of a particular language, for example, when talking about the phraseology of the German language (Burger 2003, 11; Fleischer 1982, 9).

Phraseologisms have certain characteristics:

1. A phraseological unit consists of at least two words.

2. Words within a phraseological unit form a certain stable combination, which is not always easy to understand based only on the meaning of each word separately.

The lexical components of a phraseological unit are often called "components of a phraseological unit"(Burger 2003,11).

Burger et al. (1982) define phraseological units as follows: they are phrases consisting of two or more words that:

- cannot be fully explained by their syntactic and semantic properties.
- They are used in the language community in the same way as ordinary words.

There is a one-way relationship between these two characteristics: if the first one applies, then the second one also applies, but not vice versa (Burger et al. 1982,1).

Definition of phraseological units according to Burger et al. (1982) seems stricter:

1. Opacity of syntax and semantics: A phrase cannot be fully explained by its syntactic and semantic properties.

2. Sustainable use: Used in the language community in a similar way to the word.

At the same time, Burger et al. (1982) argue that if a phrase matches the first characteristic, it automatically matches the second, but not vice versa.

Comparison of definitions

It is worth noting that the definitions of Burger (2003) and Burger et al. (1982) are different: the definition of Burger et al. is stricter. Definition by Burger et al. corresponds to what Burger (2003) calls phraseology in the narrow sense.

Examples of phraseological units according to Burger (2003)

1. Guten Appetit!- Polite form of starting a joint meal; Formula for desire at the sight of food.
2. Verschiebe nicht auf morgen, was du heute kannst besorgen- Don't put off until tomorrow what you can do today.
3. an jmdm einen Narren gefressen haben- To love someone very much or to be carried away by someone.
4. hin and her- Back and forth; constant change of direction.
5. sich die Zähne putzen- Brush your teeth.
6. das Rote Kreuz- Red Cross.

Phraseologisms are a special linguistic object that has a number of characteristic properties. The main criteria that determine a phraseological unit are:

1. Polylexicality: Phraseologisms consist of more than one word.
2. Hardness: They are used in the language community in a similar way to a single word.

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BORROWING BRILLIANCE: CHALLENGES OF IMPLEMENTING FOREIGN LANGUAGE INNOVATIONS

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Annotation: while foreign experience and innovative technologies hold immense potential for improving foreign language learning, navigating the challenges is critical. By carefully considering cultural context, ensuring equitable access, and investing in teacher training, educators can turn borrowed brilliance into effective learning experiences for all students